

THE TIME OF SETTING AND CHANGES IN H-ION CONCENTRATION DURING THE SETTING OF GELS FORMED BY THE INTERACTION OF OPPOSITELY CHARGED SOLS. PART II. THE INTERACTION OF NICKEL HYDROXIDE AND MANGANESE DIOXIDE SOLS WITH ALUMINIUM HYDROXIDE SOL

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The time of setting of the gels obtained by mixing negatively charged sols of (i) nickel hydroxide and (ii) manganese dioxide with positively charged sol of aluminium hydroxide has been measured at 35°. The relation $t = Ra^{-n}$ is found to hold between the time of setting (t) and the volume (a), of the oppositely charged sols. No appreciable changes in pH take place during the formation of these gels.

It is well known that mutual coagulation takes place when oppositely charged sols are mixed together in suitable proportions. Prasad and Mehta (*Current Sci.*, 1943, 12, 19) have found that when oppositely charged sols of suitable concentrations are mixed together under certain conditions, gel-formation takes place. Attempts have, therefore, been made to determine whether the formation of gels by this method follows the same behaviour as observed with gels prepared by other methods.

This investigation deals with the determination of the time of setting and the changes in the H-ion concentration taking place during the setting of the gels formed by mixing the negatively charged sols of (i) nickel hydroxide and (ii) manganese dioxide, with the positively charged sol of aluminium hydroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Aluminium Hydroxide Sol.—Aluminium hydroxide sol was prepared by Crum's method and its colloidal content was found to correspond to 0.235 g. of Al_2O_3 per 100 c.c. of the sol.

Preparation of the Nickel Hydroxide Sol.—It was prepared by a method found by the authors. Nickel hydroxide precipitated by the addition of approximately 2.0N-NaOH solution to a 10% solution of nickel chloride was washed free from chloride ions and then dissolved in 30 g. of tartaric acid. The required amount of 2.0 N-NaOH was then added to the clear solution which rapidly set to a clear transparent gel which on shaking with distilled water dispersed completely and gave rise to the transparent green-coloured stable sol. It was negatively charged and its colloidal content corresponded to 0.301 g. of nickel per 100 c.c. of the sol.

Preparation of Manganese Dioxide Sol.—It was prepared by the reduction of potassium permanganate with sodium arsenite and its colloidal content corresponded to 0.057 g. of MnO_2 per 100 c.c. of the sol.

Method of Measuring the Time of Setting.—The time of setting was measured at 35°, in an air thermostat by Hurd and Letteron's method (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 604) in which certain modifications were introduced for the sake of accuracy.

Procedure.—A number of test tubes were filled with 5 c.c. of the aluminium hydroxide sol. In another set of test tubes different known volumes of the oppositely charged sols were taken and diluted with distilled water so as to make up their volume to 5 c.c. Both sets of test tubes were put in the air thermostat to attain the constant temperature. The two sols were then mixed

a number of times and well shaken. The mixture was then immediately transferred to a small weighing bottle, and a glass rod $3''$ long and 1 mm. in diameter was inserted in position; a stop-watch was also started simultaneously. The time required for the glass rod to remain in position when the supporting rod is removed is the time of setting of the gel. To increase the accuracy of the measurements a number of readings were taken, each time disturbing the gel-forming mixture as few times as possible. The minimum time obtained in this manner was taken as the time of setting of the gel.

The small volumes of the oppositely charged sols were measured out from a micro-pipette measuring up to 0.01 c.c. The results obtained are given in the following tables in which $a = e.a.$ of the oppositely charged sol, and $t =$ time of setting in minutes.

TABLE I

Nickel hydroxide sol. $m = 36.66$. $\log R = -3.50$.

a .	t .	$\log a$.	$\log t$ (obs.).	$\log t$ (calc.).
0.80	1.0	-0.0969	0.0000	0.052
0.79	1.5	-0.1024	0.1761	0.254
0.78	3.0	-0.1079	0.4771	0.457
0.77	5.0	-0.1135	0.6990	0.661
0.76	8.0	-0.1192	0.9031	0.870
0.75	13.0	-0.1249	1.1139	1.078
0.74	19.0	-0.1308	1.2788	1.294
0.73	27.0	-0.1367	1.4314	1.512

TABLE II

Manganese dioxide sol. $m = 10.24$. $\log R = 4.20$.

a .	t .	$\log a$.	$\log t$ (obs.).	$\log t$ (calc.).
2.50	1.5	0.3979	0.1761	0.123
2.40	2.0	0.3802	0.3010	0.305
2.30	3.0	0.3617	0.4771	0.491
2.20	5.0	0.3434	0.6990	0.693
2.10	8.0	0.3222	0.9031	0.804
2.00	12.5	0.3020	1.0969	1.116
1.90	22.5	0.2788	1.3522	1.347
1.80	35.0	0.2553	1.5502	1.584

Measurement of p_H during Gel-formation.—The H-ion concentration of the two gel-forming mixtures from each set were measured by means of Coleman's electrometer at various intervals during and after setting until no change was observed. For this purpose 5 c.c. of the aluminium hydroxide sol were taken in one test tube and in another were taken the selected volumes of the oppositely charged sols and distilled water to make up the volume to 5 c.c.. The contents of the two test tubes were mixed together and well shaken and the mixture was introduced in the electrometer; a stop-watch was also started at the same time. The electrometer was standardised and occasionally checked by means of standard buffer solutions. The results obtained are given in the following table in which t represents the time in minutes after introducing the gel-forming mixture in the electrometer, at which the p_H readings were taken.

TABLE III

t .	1.0	2.5	5.0	7.5	10.0
		0.74 C.c. of nickel hydroxide sol.			
p_H	4.10	4.10	—	—	—
		0.75 C.c. of nickel hydroxide sol.			
p_H	4.06	4.06	4.07	4.08	4.08
		1.80 C.c. of manganese dioxide sol.			
p_H	3.89		3.90	—	—
		2.00 C.c. of manganese dioxide sol.			
p_H	3.96	3.96	—	—	—

DISCUSSION

The gels formed in the presence of both the nickel hydroxide and manganese dioxide sols are quite transparent and thixotropic. It is therefore clear that all the conditions (*cf.* Prasad, Presidential Address, *Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1940) required for the formation of gels prepared by other methods, are satisfied in the mode of gel-formation described in this paper.

It will be seen that the time of setting of gels decreases at first rapidly and then slowly as increasing quantities of the oppositely charged sols are added to the same volume of the aluminium hydroxide sol. These results are of the same nature as those obtained in the case of gels prepared by the addition of electrolytes and by mixing the oppositely charged sols of ferric and aluminium hydroxides to the nickel hydroxide sol (Prasad and Mehta, *loc. cit.*).

On plotting $\log a$ against $\log t$, the curves obtained are straight lines. Same results have been obtained in the case of gels prepared by (i) the addition of electrolytes to sols by Dube and Prakash (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1940, 11, 331) and (ii) mixing oppositely charged sols by Prasad and Mehta (*loc. cit.*). This confirms the conclusion that the formation of gels by mixing oppositely charged sols is similar to that obtained by other methods. Further the relation between a and t is given by $t = Ra^{-m}$, in which m and R are constants. This expression is of the same type as put forward by Prasad and Hattiangadi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 6, 653) and by Dube and Prakash (*loc. cit.*).

The values of m and $\log R$ calculated from any two values of a and t in a particular set of results are given at the top of each table. It will be seen that they are different in each case.

These values of m and R have been used for calculating the values of t for the various values of a employed in this investigation and the results obtained are given in the fifth columns of Tables I and II. A comparison of the calculated and observed values of t shows that the expression $t = Ra^{-m}$ reproduces the experimental results fairly accurately.

The p_{α} values of various gel-forming mixtures do not increase appreciably as happens during the setting of several inorganic gels studied by Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 391) and Prasad and Mehta (*loc. cit.*).

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Received January 20, 1943.